

HAL
open science

Unsupervised anomaly detection in brain FDG PET with deep generative models: An experimental analysis of model variability and mitigation strategies

Maëlys Solal, Pascaline André, Ninon Burgos

► To cite this version:

Maëlys Solal, Pascaline André, Ninon Burgos. Unsupervised anomaly detection in brain FDG PET with deep generative models: An experimental analysis of model variability and mitigation strategies. SPIE Medical Imaging 2026, Feb 2026, Vancouver, Canada. <hal-05340039v2>

HAL Id: hal-05340039

<https://inria.hal.science/hal-05340039v2>

Submitted on 2 Feb 2026

HAL is a multi-disciplinary open access archive for the deposit and dissemination of scientific research documents, whether they are published or not. The documents may come from teaching and research institutions in France or abroad, or from public or private research centers.

L'archive ouverte pluridisciplinaire **HAL**, est destinée au dépôt et à la diffusion de documents scientifiques de niveau recherche, publiés ou non, émanant des établissements d'enseignement et de recherche français ou étrangers, des laboratoires publics ou privés.

HAL Authorization

Unsupervised anomaly detection in brain FDG PET with deep generative models: An experimental analysis of model variability and mitigation strategies

Maëlys Solal^a, Pascaline André^a, and Ninon Burgos^a

^aSorbonne Université, Institut du Cerveau - Paris Brain Institute - ICM, CNRS, Inria, Inserm, AP-HP, Hôpital de la Pitié Salpêtrière, F-75013, Paris, France

ABSTRACT

Unsupervised anomaly detection allows identifying anomalies from unlabeled data, making it useful for neuroimaging analysis and computer-aided diagnosis. Given an individual’s scan, we use a generative model to construct a subject-specific image of healthy appearance and compare both images to identify anomalies. Designing anomaly maps in such way has drawbacks as the reconstructions are imperfect and some variability is not taken into account. We study model variability arising from using different random seeds during training and explore strategies to mitigate the effect of unwanted reconstruction errors and variability. Our experiments on 3D brain FDG PET scans from ADNI suggest that variance between models can be reduced by aggregating their reconstructions in a Z-score based anomaly map, or normalizing the anomaly map with a healthy validation set.

Keywords: Unsupervised anomaly detection, Deep generative models, Variability study

1. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning methods have shown promise in the quantitative analysis of neuroimaging data.¹ They enable the detection of subtle changes in brain patterns amid natural variations, a critical aspect in the early diagnosis of neurodegenerative disorders. Within the unsupervised anomaly detection (UAD) framework, machine learning algorithms are used to identify rare events from unlabeled data, facilitating the detection of various anomalies,²⁻⁴ including those associated with different dementia subtypes such as Alzheimer’s.⁵⁻⁷

Reconstruction-based anomaly detection methods rely on generating a subject-specific image of healthy appearance and then comparing the subject’s real image with this synthetic image, resulting in a personalized map of anomalies. First, generative models such as variational autoencoders (VAEs), generative adversarial networks, or diffusion models are trained exclusively on healthy images to learn the healthy distribution. Second, at inference time, the model is fed a patient’s image (with potential anomalies) and reconstructs the image based on its learned healthy distribution.² Ideally, the model should reconstruct healthy tissue only, and we hypothesize that the reconstructed image is a subject-specific pseudo-healthy representation of the input image.^{2,8,9} Finally, anomaly maps can be defined as the reconstruction error, or residual, that is, the voxel-wise difference between the patient’s input image and the model’s output image, such that high values indicate anomalies.^{2,8,9} However, this residual-based approach has several shortcomings: residuals depend on the underlying raw intensities, there is no natural thresholding mechanism, and it is hard to distinguish between reconstruction errors due to genuine pathological anomalies and reconstruction errors due to the model’s imperfect reconstructions, leading to false positive detections even in healthy tissues.¹⁰⁻¹²

Several approaches have been proposed to address these issues: post-processing techniques,^{8,13,14} leveraging multiple reconstructions,¹⁵⁻¹⁷ alternative metrics,¹⁸ and uncertainty estimation techniques.^{11,12,19} There is no standard post-processing procedure, neither of the pseudo-healthy reconstruction, nor of the anomaly map. Common steps include applying a body contour mask, morphological operations, median kernel filtering, normalization, thresholding of the anomaly map, connected component analysis, and adaptive histograms.^{8,13,14}

Send correspondence to Maëlys Solal (maelys.solal@icm-institute.org) or Ninon Burgos (ninon.burgos@cnrs.fr).

To account for the model’s reconstruction errors, several studies have used multiple reconstructions rather than a single reconstruction, which can easily be done in VAEs and diffusion models. Some approaches compare the average reconstruction with the input image.^{8,15} Patel et al.¹⁶ fit a kernel density estimation independently for each voxel position to obtain a probability density function for intensities. Behrendt et al.¹⁷ considered the covariance of pixels between reconstructions and voxels of the image. Huijben et al.¹⁸ explored alternative metrics to the absolute reconstruction error, including metrics based on components of the SSIM,²⁰ perceptual metrics and metric ensembles. Other works are based on uncertainty estimation, where the anomaly maps are normalized by uncertainty, or the estimated variance of individual pixels.^{11,12,19}

In this work, we unveil various sources of variability in a reconstruction-based anomaly detection pipeline and study their impact on reconstruction errors and anomaly detection performance. We focus on variability arising from the random seed used during training (which affects weight initialization, data augmentation, and data ordering) and explore strategies including model ensembling, anomaly map normalization to improve the reliability of anomaly detection pipelines and their evaluation. We compare these approaches in the context of dementia-related anomalies on 3D FDG PET using a variational autoencoder. Our experimental comparative analysis emphasizes that it is crucial to design robust anomaly maps, and to mitigate the impact of randomness-induced variability to support more stable and trustworthy deployment in real-world clinical practice.

2. METHODS

2.1 Generative model

To generate subject-specific pseudo-healthy images, we rely on VAEs,²¹ specifically a β -VAE.²² The β -VAE model is built around two components: an encoder and a decoder. The encoder $q_\phi(z|x)$ maps each observation $x \in \mathcal{X}$ into a compact latent representation $z \in \mathbb{R}^d$. The decoder $p_\theta(x|z)$ then attempts to reconstruct the observation from this latent code. A common formulation assumes that the encoder outputs a Gaussian distribution, $q_\phi(z|x) = \mathcal{N}(\mu(x), \sigma(x))$, while the decoder models the likelihood as $p_\theta(x|z) = \mathcal{N}(\mathcal{D}(z), 1)$, where μ , σ , and \mathcal{D} are implemented as neural networks. Training consists of minimizing a loss composed of a reconstruction term and a regularization term:

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \mathbb{E}_{z \sim q_\phi(z|x)} [\log p_\theta(x|z)] - \beta \text{KL}(q_\phi(z|x) || p(z)). \quad (1)$$

The first part encourages the decoder to accurately reconstruct x from z , while the second part penalizes deviations of the encoder’s output distribution from the prior $p(z) = \mathcal{N}(0, I)$ using the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence. The coefficient β adjusts how strongly this KL term influences the learned latent space. The training and inference process are depicted in Figure 1. Note that in most cases, and unless stated otherwise, during training, we sample the latent code, $z \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu(x), \sigma(x))$, whereas at inference, we set $z = \mu(x)$ as shown in Figure 1.

The model is trained exclusively on healthy data to learn the healthy distribution. At inference time, the model is fed an image with potential anomalies (which we denote \mathbf{x}), and reconstructs the image based on its learned healthy distribution, we call this image the pseudo-healthy reconstruction (which we denote by $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$). By comparing the input image \mathbf{x} and its pseudo-healthy reconstruction $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$, we can identify anomalies (see Figure 1).

We choose to use VAE models since they are computationally lightweight compared to diffusion models, making it feasible to run extensive experiments on 3D images. Moreover, their inherently imperfect reconstructions make them well-suited for studying the impact of various sources of variability on the reconstruction error.

2.1.1 Obtaining multiple pseudo-healthy reconstructions

In this paper, we study various sources of variability in a pseudo-healthy reconstruction pipeline. We are therefore interested in obtaining multiple reconstructions $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i$ per input image \mathbf{x} rather than a single reconstruction $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$. We do so in two different ways: (i) by training multiple models with varying random seeds, and (ii) by sampling multiple times in the model’s latent space.

Figure 1: Typical procedure for VAE-based pseudo-healthy reconstruction and residual-based anomaly map. For training (top), the model is shown exclusively healthy data, and the latent code is sampled using the reparameterization trick. For inference (bottom), the model is fed an image with potential anomalies (\mathbf{x}), and reconstructs the image based on its learned distribution, using $z = \mu(x)$, and obtaining a pseudo-healthy reconstruction ($\hat{\mathbf{x}}$). An anomaly map can be obtained by comparing the input image and its pseudo-healthy reconstruction, typically using the residual, $\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}$.

(i) **Training models with varying random seeds** We train $N_s = 11$ models with random seeds ranging from 0 to 10. All models are trained with an identical training procedure on the same dataset. The only sources of variation are in the random initialization of model weights, the stochastic nature of data augmentation (with fixed parameters but random sampling), and the order in which data is shown during training. This setup allows studying the variability of a β -VAE with respect to its random seed, resulting in 11 distinct models and therefore 11 different reconstructions for each input image. We denote by $\mu_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ and $\sigma_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ the mean and standard deviation of the N_s reconstructions $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq N_s}$ obtained for an input image \mathbf{x} . This process is represented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Using N_s models trained with varying random seeds to obtain multiple pseudo-healthy reconstructions. We denote by VAE_i the model trained with random seed i and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i$ the pseudo-healthy reconstruction for an input image \mathbf{x} . The mean $\mu_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ and standard deviation $\sigma_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ of all reconstructions $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq N_s}$ are computed, in order to obtain two different types of anomaly maps: $\mathbf{r}_{\text{seeds}}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x} - \mu_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ and $\mathbf{z}_{\text{seeds}}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\mathbf{x} - \mu_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}})}{\sigma_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}})}$.

(ii) **Sampling in the latent space** It is also possible to obtain multiple reconstructions from a single trained model, rather than training multiple models to obtain multiple reconstructions. Recall that, in a VAE, an image

\mathbf{x} is encoded to obtain the mean $\mu(\mathbf{x})$ and standard deviation $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$ of the latent distribution. At inference time, rather than setting $\mathbf{z} = \mu(\mathbf{x})$, we can sample $N_l = 10$ latent codes $\mathbf{z}_i \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu(\mathbf{x}), \sigma(\mathbf{x}))$ and decode each to obtain the corresponding reconstructions $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i$. This approach enables us to obtain multiple reconstructions “for free” by introducing stochasticity only at the latent sampling stage, a natural property of VAEs. We denote by $\mu_l(\mathbf{x})$ and $\sigma_l(\mathbf{x})$ the mean and standard deviation of the N_l reconstructions $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq N_l}$ obtained for an input \mathbf{x} . This process is represented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Sampling the latent space at inference time to obtain N_l pseudo-healthy reconstructions using a single trained VAE model. At inference time, for an input image \mathbf{x} , we encode it to obtain $\mu(\mathbf{x})$ and $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$, and sample a latent code $\mathbf{z}_i \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu(\mathbf{x}), \sigma(\mathbf{x}))$ using the reparameterization trick, which we decode to obtain $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i$, the pseudo-healthy reconstruction. By repeating the process N_l times, we obtain N_l reconstructions $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq N_l}$, from which we compute the mean $\mu_l(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ and standard deviation $\sigma_l(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$, in order to obtain two different types of anomaly maps: $\mathbf{r}_{\text{latent}}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x} - \mu_l(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ and $\mathbf{z}_{\text{latent}}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\mathbf{x} - \mu_l(\hat{\mathbf{x}})}{\sigma_l(\hat{\mathbf{x}})}$.

2.2 Dataset

Our dataset consists of 3D FDG PET scans from the ADNI database.^{23–25} For our main dataset, we select images that are coregistered, averaged, and uniformized to the same resolution (8 mm FWHM), to minimize heterogeneity due to the use of different scanners. For our additional validation and testing datasets (see Section 3.3.1), we also include images that are coregistered, and averaged, but not uniformized to the same resolution (with effective resolution ranging from 4.5 mm to 7.5 mm FWHM, see <https://adni.loni.usc.edu/data-samples/adni-data/neuroimaging/pet/> for more detail). We process them using the `pet-linear` pipeline from Clinica,²⁶ which affinely registers to the MNI space, normalizes in intensity using the average PET uptake in the cerebellum and pons regions and crops each image. We select images from stable healthy participants that are constantly labeled as cognitively normal (CN) in ADNI for a 3-year interval. We use 545 images from 302 healthy subjects for training, 25 images from 25 healthy subjects for validation. For testing, we use 50 images from 50 healthy subjects, and also include 50 images from 50 Alzheimer’s disease (AD) patients. These data splits were performed at the subject’s level and stratified by sex and age to avoid data leakage and reduce biases.

2.3 Evaluation procedure

In this section, we detail our evaluation procedure. The different steps presented here are summarized in the diagram in Figure 4.

2.3.1 Healthy-to-healthy reconstruction

We first evaluate our model’s ability to reconstruct healthy images. We use the structural similarity (SSIM)²⁰ and MSE metrics. We denote by hhSSIM (resp. hhMSE), the SSIM (resp. MSE) between a healthy input \mathbf{x} and its reconstruction $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$.

Figure 4: Diagram of our evaluation procedure and corresponding metrics. Plain arrows correspond to our typical pseudo-healthy reconstruction pipeline, dashed arrows to our anomaly simulation procedure and colored lines to the metric computation. It is represented in the simple case of residual-based anomaly maps and single reconstruction, but the framework is general and can be adapted to all situations described in the paper.

2.3.2 Abnormal-to-healthy reconstruction

We then wish to evaluate our model’s ability to reconstruct abnormal images as healthy, and anomaly detection performance. Since ground truth pairs of healthy and abnormal images are unavailable, we rely on the simulation framework introduced by Hassanaly et al.⁷ to simulate realistic hypometabolism characteristic of various dementia subtypes with different degrees of severity. We denote by \mathbf{x}' the simulated abnormal image obtained from a healthy image \mathbf{x} .

This framework is used to quantitatively evaluate our models. It allows evaluating the abnormal-to-healthy reconstruction quality, by comparing the pseudo-healthy image generated from simulated abnormal input $\hat{\mathbf{x}}'$ and the ground-truth healthy image \mathbf{x} . Similarly as above, we use the SSIM and the MSE metrics, which we now denote by ahSSIM and ahMSE.

2.3.3 Voxel-level anomaly map

Once we have, for each input \mathbf{x} , its (single) pseudo-healthy reconstruction $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$, or its (multiple) pseudo-healthy reconstructions $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i$, we design our anomaly maps in different manners.

Our baseline is the residual-based anomaly map $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}$. Given the limitations of residual-based anomaly maps,¹⁰ we include in our experiments SSIM-based anomaly maps, where we compute the SSIM (with window size 11) between the input and the pseudo-healthy reconstruction(s) (rather than the difference).^{17,18}

Moreover, to account for the model’s reconstruction errors, we design anomaly maps that are obtained from multiple reconstructions rather than a single reconstruction. These are designed in different ways: the difference (or SSIM) between the input image and the mean of the reconstructions, and a Z-score with the multiple reconstructions. Recall that we denote by $\mu_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ and $\sigma_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ the mean and standard deviation of the reconstructions $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq N_s}$ obtained with the N_s models with different random seeds. Similarly, we denote by $\mu_l(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ and $\sigma_l(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ the mean and standard deviation of the reconstructions $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq N_l}$ obtained by sampling N_l times in the latent space.

Figure 5: Summary table of all possible anomaly maps, obtained from a single trained VAE model, from multiple models trained with different random seeds, or from sampling different latent codes in the latent space, and compared and aggregated in different manners. The top row corresponds to raw anomaly maps, and the bottom row to anomaly maps normalized using the healthy control validation set. We represent a central axial slice from the anomaly maps obtained from an input image with simulated AD at severity 30.

In total, there are eight different anomaly map designs (globally denoted by $\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x})$) and represented in Figure 5:

- (i) $\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}$,
- (ii) $\mathbf{r}_{\text{SSIM}}(\mathbf{x}) = 1 - \text{SSIM}(\mathbf{x}, \hat{\mathbf{x}})$,
- (iii) $\mathbf{r}_{\text{latent}}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x} - \mu_l(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$,
- (iv) $\mathbf{z}_{\text{latent}}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\mathbf{x} - \mu_l(\hat{\mathbf{x}})}{\sigma_l(\hat{\mathbf{x}})}$
- (v) $\mathbf{r}_{\text{latentSSIM}}(\mathbf{x}) = 1 - \text{SSIM}(\mathbf{x}, \mu_l(\hat{\mathbf{x}}))$
- (vi) $\mathbf{r}_{\text{seeds}}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x} - \mu_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$
- (vii) $\mathbf{z}_{\text{seeds}}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\mathbf{x} - \mu_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}})}{\sigma_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}})}$
- (viii) $\mathbf{r}_{\text{seedsSSIM}}(\mathbf{x}) = 1 - \text{SSIM}(\mathbf{x}, \mu_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}}))$

In addition, we eventually normalize each anomaly map $\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x})$ using a healthy validation set. We set

$$\tilde{\mathbf{a}}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}) - \mu_{\text{HC}}(\mathbf{a})}{\sigma_{\text{HC}}(\mathbf{a})},$$

where $\mu_{\text{HC}}(\mathbf{a})$ and $\sigma_{\text{HC}}(\mathbf{a})$ are the mean and standard deviation of \mathbf{a} across all images in a healthy validation set (HC). We represent this normalization step in the diagram in Figure 6 in the simple case of the residual anomaly map, and all anomaly maps derived from this process in Figure 5. Note that the choice of healthy validation set is explored in Section 3.3.1.

We evaluate the voxel-level anomaly detection performance by comparing the unthresholded anomaly map with the simulation mask. For this, we compute the voxel-wise average precision (denoted AP_{vox}) and an estimate of the best possible Dice index ($\lceil \text{Dice} \rceil$).

2.3.4 Sample-level anomaly score

We design sample-level anomaly scores as the mean of voxels of the absolute value of our anomaly map. We evaluate these using sample-wise AUC and AP (healthy vs abnormal, for each evaluation group separately). We binarize the scores using the 95th percentile of the scores on the healthy validation set and compute the accuracy.

Figure 6: Diagram of the normalization of anomaly maps using the anomaly maps obtained from a healthy control validation set. The diagram represents the simple case where the anomaly map is a simple residual between input and output, but the process can be extended for all anomaly map types. We set $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}) - \mu_{\text{HC}}(\mathbf{r})}{\sigma_{\text{HC}}(\mathbf{r})}$, where $\mu_{\text{HC}}(\mathbf{r})$ and $\sigma_{\text{HC}}(\mathbf{r})$ are the mean and standard deviation of \mathbf{r} across all images in a healthy validation set (HC).

2.4 Implementation detail

2.4.1 VAE architecture and training

In terms of architecture, we choose the 3D β -VAE proposed in Hassanaly et al.²⁷ since it showed good performance on the benchmark²⁷ comparing VAE variants focused on detecting dementia-related lesions in FDG PET images.

Its encoder is composed of five convolutional layers and a dense layer, and its decoder is symmetrical, by adding an upsampling layer before each convolution. After each convolutional layer is a batch normalization and a swish activation function, except for the last layer, where there is no batch normalization, and the activation function is a sigmoid.

We perform data augmentation during training: random noise (with standard deviation 2) and random blur (with standard deviation 0.02) from torchio.²⁸ We found that such change slightly increases the model performance in terms of healthy-to-healthy reconstruction (hhSSIM increases from 0.860 ± 0.025 to 0.874 ± 0.022), and anomaly detection on simulated images (AP_{vox} on AD-30 increases from 0.407 ± 0.084 to 0.469 ± 0.080).

We keep all other training parameters the same: the latent space has size 256, we set $\beta = 10$, we train the model for 200 epochs, with learning rate 10^{-4} and batch size 8 using ClinicaDL.²⁹

2.4.2 Summary of validation and testing datasets

Using the simulation framework described in Section 2.3.2,⁷ we obtain five evaluation groups which differ in lesion size, location and severity: three groups of Alzheimer’s disease (AD) with increasing degrees of severity (AD-15, AD-30, AD-50), and two groups of medium severity for two other dementia subtypes, namely the behavioral variant of fronto-temporal dementia (bvFTD-30), and the semantic-variant of primary progressive aphasia (svPPA-30), all shown in Figure 7.

We also perform a sensitivity analysis to study the impact of the healthy-control normalization group on the anomaly map normalization (see Section 3.3.1), i.e. going from $\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x})$ to $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}) - \mu_{\text{HC}}(\mathbf{a})}{\sigma_{\text{HC}}(\mathbf{a})}$. For these experiments, we use two additional validation groups and five additional testing groups. The first additional validation group consists of images with simulated low-severity AD, denoted by val-AD-15. The second additional validation group consists of the healthy validation images with mixed resolutions, rather than uniformized resolutions,

Figure 7: Summary table of the anomalies simulated (AD, bvFTD and svPPA) with varying degrees of severity for the same subject, with the corresponding healthy image (right). Top: binary pathology mask used for the hypometabolism simulation. Bottom: simulated abnormal image, with the pathological region circled in red. The images are sagittal slices (at index 60) of the same subject, overlaid with the MNI template.

denoted by val-CN-mres. Finally, the five additional testing groups consist in the same test images as described above, but in their mixed resolution version.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Variance of models trained with different random seeds

We observe a large variability in the performance of models trained with different random seeds, with considerably greater variability in anomaly detection metrics (AP_{vox} and [Dice]) than in abnormal-to-healthy reconstruction metrics (ahSSIM and ahMSE). The results for the evaluation group AD-30 (representative of the other groups) for the residual-based anomaly map \mathbf{r} (most typical anomaly map design) are shown in Figure 8. Similar patterns are observed for all groups and anomaly map designs (see Appendix A.1).

In the context of standard deep learning workflows, where the impact of random seeds is often overlooked, this implies that the same model architecture can yield significantly different results depending on its initialization, potentially leading to substantial over- or under-performance, and biased evaluation.

Figure 8: Reconstruction and anomaly detection performance on AD-30 images for residual map \mathbf{r} .

3.2 Strategy 1: Z-score to aggregate outputs from models trained with different random seeds

Given the variability between models, we propose to aggregate the reconstructions obtained by all models and design a Z-score-based anomaly map denoted by $\mathbf{z}_{\text{seeds}}$. Recall that, for an input image \mathbf{x} ,

$$\mathbf{z}_{\text{seeds}}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}})}{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_s(\hat{\mathbf{x}})},$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s(\mathbf{x})$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_s(\mathbf{x})$ are the mean and standard deviation of the $N_s = 11$ reconstructions $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq N_s}$ obtained by training N_s models with varying random seeds.

In Figure 9, we plot the AP scores obtained with residual anomaly maps of individual models \mathbf{r} (in blue) and with the proposed $\mathbf{z}_{\text{seeds}}$ (in orange). We observe that $\mathbf{z}_{\text{seeds}}$ outperforms all individual models for AD-15, AD-30, and svPPA-30 in terms of mean and median. For bvFTD-30, it outperforms all models in terms of median and all but two in terms of mean. For AD-50, it outperforms all but two in terms of mean and all but four models in terms of median.

Similar results were observed with other anomaly map designs than residuals (see Appendix A.2).

Figure 9: AP for all groups of residual-based anomaly maps \mathbf{r} of models trained with random seeds 0-10 (in the x-axis, in blue) compared to $\mathbf{z}_{\text{seeds}}$ anomaly maps (in orange) built from the predictions of all models.

3.3 Strategy 2: Normalization of anomaly maps using the healthy validation set

Since training multiple models with varying random seeds is computationally expensive (even though ideal), we explore alternative strategies to reduce variance and mitigate the impact of random seed initialization.

We turn to normalizing the anomaly map using a healthy validation set, which not only allows for reducing the effect of the random seed on the performance variance, but should also account for a portion of the reconstruction error due to model imperfections and should capture the variability present in healthy data. For a given input image \mathbf{x} and a given anomaly map $\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x})$, we normalize it using a healthy validation set and obtain

$$\tilde{\mathbf{a}}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}) - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\text{HC}}(\mathbf{a})}{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{HC}}(\mathbf{a})},$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\text{HC}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{HC}}$ are the mean and standard deviation of \mathbf{a} across all images in a healthy validation set (HC).

In Figure 10, we report the AP for \mathbf{r} and $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}$ across different random seeds for all evaluation groups. We observe a clear reduction in performance variability: the worst-performing models show substantial improvement, while the best-performing models maintain similar performance. We even observe a general increase in AP (from 0.1 to 0.3) for the svPPA-30 group.

Results for other anomaly maps are presented in Appendix A.3.

Figure 10: AP without (left) and with (right) healthy-control validation-based normalization.

3.3.1 Sensitivity analysis: impact of the validation set quality

We then conduct a sensitivity analysis to assess the robustness of our normalization procedure. Our investigation focuses on two specific scenarios: (i) the case where the validation set is contaminated and contains anomalies, and (ii) the case where a distribution shift occurs between the training and test sets.

To examine the first scenario, we use the val-AD-15 validation set, where we introduced low-severity AD anomalies into all images. As shown in the top table of Table 1 (first two rows), performance degrades when normalization is performed using val-AD-15 instead of val-CN. The drop is especially large for the svPPA-30 group, which is consistent with the fact that detecting small-scale anomalies is even more challenging. This experiment confirms that the normalization step requires a validation set that is as clean and anomaly-free as possible.

For the second scenario, we introduce a distribution shift by using data with non-uniform resolution, which we refer to as mixed resolution. Our goal is to determine whether normalization should rely on data closer to the training distribution or closer to the inference distribution. In all experiments, the models are trained on images with uniform resolution, for validation, we use either uniform-resolution data (val-CN) or mixed-resolution data (val-CN-mres). In the top table of Table 1, the test set also has uniform resolution, whereas in the bottom table, the test set uses mixed resolutions. Across both settings, we observe that normalizing with images with uniform resolution (val-CN) consistently outperforms normalization with mixed resolutions (val-CN-mres). This suggests that normalization should be performed using data that match the training distribution rather than the inference distribution.

3.4 Strategy 3: Anomaly map designs

As an alternative approach to reduce variability and mitigate reconstruction errors, we explore other anomaly map designs and report these in Figure 11.

First, we test replacing the standard voxel-wise intensity difference with the SSIM between the input and the pseudo-healthy reconstruction, with \mathbf{r}_{SSIM} , $\mathbf{r}_{\text{latentSSIM}}$ and $\mathbf{r}_{\text{seedSSIM}}$. In our experiments, this approach does not lead to performance improvements, on the contrary, SSIM-based maps consistently yield worse anomaly detection performance compared to standard residual maps. We also evaluate anomaly maps based on multiple reconstructions: $\mathbf{r}_{\text{latent}}$, $\mathbf{z}_{\text{latent}}$, $\mathbf{r}_{\text{seeds}}$ and $\mathbf{z}_{\text{seeds}}$. We find that the usual residual \mathbf{r} and $\mathbf{r}_{\text{latent}}$ produced comparable results, while $\mathbf{z}_{\text{latent}}$ perform poorly, likely due to unstable and low standard deviation values. As previously shown, $\mathbf{z}_{\text{seeds}}$ (and $\mathbf{r}_{\text{seeds}}$), even though computationally expensive, remain very strong-performing.

Table 1: Mean (\pm std) AP across the 11 models trained with different random seeds for residual maps normalized using different healthy control validation groups: the usual healthy-control validation group (val-CN), images with simulated low-severity AD (val-AD-15), and healthy-control validation images with mixed (rather than uniform) resolutions (val-CN-mres). The highest values (in terms of mean) are highlighted in **bold**.

(a) Evaluation on our usual testing sets with images with uniform resolutions

	AD-15	AD-30	AD-50	svPPA-30	bvFTD-30
val-CN	0.268 \pm 0.034	0.526 \pm 0.061	0.826 \pm 0.029	0.319 \pm 0.105	0.439 \pm 0.092
val-AD-15	0.209 \pm 0.013	0.340 \pm 0.052	0.786 \pm 0.038	0.098 \pm 0.051	0.381 \pm 0.080
val-CN-mres	0.206 \pm 0.022	0.377 \pm 0.062	0.754 \pm 0.044	0.216 \pm 0.087	0.279 \pm 0.078

(b) Evaluation on the testing sets with images with mixed resolutions

	AD-15-mres	AD-30-mres	AD-50-mres	svPPA-30-mres	bvFTD-30-mres
val-CN	0.256 \pm 0.041	0.449 \pm 0.089	0.748 \pm 0.072	0.153 \pm 0.086	0.334 \pm 0.108
val-AD-15	0.208 \pm 0.015	0.304 \pm 0.053	0.68 \pm 0.082	0.055 \pm 0.03	0.316 \pm 0.098
val-CN-mres	0.226 \pm 0.037	0.381 \pm 0.085	0.718 \pm 0.075	0.131 \pm 0.075	0.263 \pm 0.087

Furthermore, we quantify the reduction in performance variability and confirm that all types of anomaly maps benefit from this validation-based normalization. In terms of mean AP between subjects, this normalization reduces variability by at least 20%, with an average reduction of more than 50% across all evaluation groups and anomaly map designs, and up to a 10-fold decrease in the best cases. We note that there are some outlier cases for the bvFTD-30 and svPPA-30 evaluation groups where the normalization increases variability.

Figure 11: Mean AP across models for each anomaly map type (with healthy-control validation-based normalization) and each evaluation group.

3.5 Validation on real Alzheimer’s data

Finally, we validate our approach on both simulated dementia and real Alzheimer’s data from the ADNI database, both qualitatively by visually inspecting the anomaly maps and quantitatively by using anomaly scores.

In Figure 12, we display examples of anomaly maps for two AD patients and in Table 2 we report the average and standard deviation across models for anomaly scores based on \tilde{r} . Overall, our anomaly scores demonstrate good classification abilities across all evaluation groups, both with real and synthetic anomalies,

Figure 12: Input image \mathbf{x} , reconstruction $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$, normalised residual $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}$ and thresholded map for two real AD patients.

with slightly worse scores for lesions of low severity (AD-15) and small size (svPPA-30). Moreover, we find that the classification accuracy of anomaly scores based on the normalized residuals $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}$ (0.725 ± 0.056) is much higher than for anomaly scores based on the raw residuals \mathbf{r} (0.355 ± 0.031) and anomaly scores based on $\mathbf{z}_{\text{seeds}}$ (0.28). In practice, this means we classify accurately around 36 out of 50 patients using scores based on $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}$ and only around 18 out of 50 patients using scores based on \mathbf{r} .

Table 2: Mean (\pm std) classification performance (abnormal vs healthy, for each evaluation group separately) across the 11 models trained with different random seeds for anomaly scores based on normalized residual anomaly maps $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}$.

Group	Accuracy	AUC	AP
AD-15	0.547 ± 0.104	0.795 ± 0.008	0.763 ± 0.012
AD-30	1.000 ± 0.000	1.000 ± 0.000	1.000 ± 0.000
AD-50	1.000 ± 0.000	1.000 ± 0.000	1.000 ± 0.000
bvFTD-30	0.931 ± 0.058	0.950 ± 0.007	0.944 ± 0.009
svPPA-30	0.347 ± 0.060	0.677 ± 0.008	0.655 ± 0.006
AD	0.725 ± 0.056	0.811 ± 0.006	0.846 ± 0.007
CN	0.804 ± 0.063	N/A	N/A

4. CONCLUSION

In this work, we highlight a largely overlooked source of variability in deep learning models: their random seed, which influences the random initialization of model weights, data augmentation (fixed parameters but random sampling) and the order in which data is presented to the model. This source of variance is clearly undesirable, especially in the context of model evaluation for tasks such as anomaly detection, so we present several approaches to mitigate its impact.

An approach is to train models with different random seeds and aggregate their reconstructions, for example using a Z-score-based method. This strategy is highly effective, but computationally expensive, as it requires training several instances of the model. As a more efficient alternative, we propose normalizing the anomaly maps using statistics computed from the validation set. We show that this normalization strategy substantially reduces performance variability across models, and even increases anomaly detection performance in certain cases. We also explore several anomaly map designs and find that, in our setting, SSIM-based maps do not outperform residual-based maps, and that maps obtained by leveraging multiple reconstructions perform similarly to the usual residual maps.

Our experiments were conducted for VAE models, on 3D brain FDG PET images with real and simulated dementia-related anomalies with different lesion size, location, and severity. Future works could assess whether these findings generalize to other types of models.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The research leading to these results has received funding from the French government under management of Agence Nationale de la Recherche as part of the “Investissements d’avenir” program (references ANR-19-P3IA-

0001 - PRAIRIE - and reference ANR-10-IAIHU-06 - IHU ICM) and the “France 2030” program (reference ANR-23-IACL-0008, PRAIRIE-PSAI), and from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Framework Program (grant number 101136607, project CLARA). This research was also funded by the Agence Nationale de la Recherche under the project “ANR-23-CE45-0005-01”.

This work was granted access to IDRIS HPC resources under the allocation AD011011648 made by GENCI.

Data collection and sharing for the Alzheimer’s Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI) is funded by the National Institute on Aging (National Institutes of Health Grant U19AG024904). The grantee organization is the Northern California Institute for Research and Education. In the past, ADNI has also received funding from the National Institute of Biomedical Imaging and Bioengineering, the Canadian Institutes of Health Research, and private sector contributions through the Foundation for the National Institutes of Health (FNIH).

REFERENCES

- [1] Burgos, N., Bottani, S., Faouzi, J., Thibeau-Sutre, E., and Colliot, O., “Deep learning for brain disorders: From data processing to disease treatment,” *Briefings in Bioinformatics* **22**, 1560–1576 (Mar. 2021).
- [2] Chen, X. and Konukoglu, E., “Unsupervised abnormality detection in medical images with deep generative methods,” in [*Biomedical Image Synthesis and Simulation*], Burgos, N. and Svoboda, D., eds., *The MICCAI Society Book Series*, 303–324, Academic Press (2022).
- [3] Bercea, C. I., Wiestler, B., Rueckert, D., and Schnabel, J. A., “Reversing the Abnormal: Pseudo-Healthy Generative Networks for Anomaly Detection,” in [*Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention – MICCAI 2023*], Greenspan, H., Madabhushi, A., Mousavi, P., Salcudean, S., Duncan, J., Syeda-Mahmood, T., and Taylor, R., eds., 293–303, Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham (2023).
- [4] Xia, T., Chartsias, A., and Tsiftaris, S. A., “Pseudo-healthy synthesis with pathology disentanglement and adversarial learning,” *Medical Image Analysis* **64**, 101719 (Aug. 2020).
- [5] Choi, H., Ha, S., Kang, H., Lee, H., and Lee, D. S., “Deep learning only by normal brain PET identify unheralded brain anomalies,” *EBioMedicine* **43**, 447–453 (May 2019).
- [6] Baydargil, H. B., Park, J.-S., and Kang, D.-Y., “Anomaly Analysis of Alzheimer’s Disease in PET Images Using an Unsupervised Adversarial Deep Learning Model,” *Applied Sciences* **11**, 2187 (Jan. 2021).
- [7] Hassanaly, R., Brianceau, C., Solal, M., Colliot, O., and Burgos, N., “Evaluation of pseudo-healthy image reconstruction for anomaly detection with deep generative models: Application to brain FDG PET,” *Machine Learning for Biomedical Imaging* **2**, 611–656 (Jan. 2024).
- [8] Baur, C., Denner, S., Wiestler, B., Navab, N., and Albarqouni, S., “Autoencoders for unsupervised anomaly segmentation in brain MR images: A comparative study,” *Medical Image Analysis* **69**, 101952 (Apr. 2021).
- [9] Schlegl, T., Seeböck, P., Waldstein, S. M., Schmidt-Erfurth, U., and Langs, G., “Unsupervised Anomaly Detection with Generative Adversarial Networks to Guide Marker Discovery,” in [*Information Processing in Medical Imaging*], Niethammer, M., Styner, M., Aylward, S., Zhu, H., Oguz, I., Yap, P.-T., and Shen, D., eds., 146–157, Springer International Publishing, Cham (2017).
- [10] Meissen, F., Wiestler, B., Kaissis, G., and Rueckert, D., “On the Pitfalls of Using the Residual Error as Anomaly Score,” in [*Proceedings of The 5th International Conference on Medical Imaging with Deep Learning*], 914–928, PMLR (Dec. 2022).
- [11] Cai, Y., Chen, H., Yang, X., Zhou, Y., and Cheng, K.-T., “Dual-distribution discrepancy with self-supervised refinement for anomaly detection in medical images,” *Medical Image Analysis* **86**, 102794 (May 2023).
- [12] Mao, Y., Xue, F.-F., Wang, R., Zhang, J., Zheng, W.-S., and Liu, H., “Abnormality Detection in Chest X-Ray Images Using Uncertainty Prediction Autoencoders,” in [*Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention – MICCAI 2020*], Martel, A. L., Abolmaesumi, P., Stoyanov, D., Mateus, D., Zuluaga, M. A., Zhou, S. K., Racoceanu, D., and Joskowicz, L., eds., 529–538, Springer International Publishing, Cham (2020).
- [13] Kascenas, A., Sanchez, P., Schremppf, P., Wang, C., Clackett, W., Mikhael, S. S., Voisey, J. P., Goatman, K., Weir, A., Pugeault, N., Tsiftaris, S. A., and O’Neil, A. Q., “The role of noise in denoising models for anomaly detection in medical images,” *Medical Image Analysis* **90**, 102963 (Dec. 2023).

- [14] Bercea, C. I., Neumayr, M., Rueckert, D., and Schnabel, J. A., “Mask, Stitch, and Re-Sample: Enhancing Robustness and Generalizability in Anomaly Detection through Automatic Diffusion Models,” in [*ICML 3rd Workshop on Interpretable Machine Learning in Healthcare (IMLH)*], (July 2023).
- [15] Baur, C., Wiestler, B., Albarqouni, S., and Navab, N., “Bayesian Skip-Autoencoders for Unsupervised Hypertense Anomaly Detection in High Resolution Brain MRI,” in [*2020 IEEE 17th International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging (ISBI)*], 1905–1909, IEEE, Iowa City, IA, USA (Apr. 2020).
- [16] Patel, A., Tudiosu, P.-D., Pinaya, W. H. L., Cook, G., Goh, V., Ourselin, S., and Cardoso, M. J., “Cross Attention Transformers for Multi-modal Unsupervised Whole-Body PET Anomaly Detection,” *Machine Learning for Biomedical Imaging* **2**, 172–201 (Apr. 2023).
- [17] Behrendt, F., Bhattacharya, D., Mieling, R., Maack, L., Krüger, J., Opfer, R., and Schlaefer, A., “Leveraging the Mahalanobis Distance to Enhance Unsupervised Brain MRI Anomaly Detection,” in [*Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention – MICCAI 2024*], Linguraru, M. G., Dou, Q., Feragen, A., Giannarou, S., Glocker, B., Lekadir, K., and Schnabel, J. A., eds., **15011**, 394–404, Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham (2024).
- [18] Huijben, E. M. C., Amirrajab, S., and Pluim, J. P. W., “Enhancing reconstruction-based out-of-distribution detection in brain MRI with model and metric ensembles,” *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine* **272**, 109045 (Dec. 2025).
- [19] Sato, K., Hama, K., Matsubara, T., and Uehara, K., “Predictable Uncertainty-Aware Unsupervised Deep Anomaly Segmentation,” in [*2019 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*], 1–7 (July 2019).
- [20] Wang, Z., Bovik, A., Sheikh, H., and Simoncelli, E., “Image Quality Assessment: From Error Visibility to Structural Similarity,” *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing* **13**, 600–612 (Apr. 2004).
- [21] Kingma, D. P. and Welling, M., “Auto-Encoding Variational Bayes,” (2014).
- [22] Higgins, I., Matthey, L., Pal, A., Burgess, C., Glorot, X., Botvinick, M., Mohamed, S., and Lerchner, A., “Beta-VAE: Learning Basic Visual Concepts with a Constrained Variational Framework,” in [*International Conference on Learning Representations*], (Nov. 2016).
- [23] Mueller, S. G., Weiner, M. W., Thal, L. J., Petersen, R. C., Jack, C., Jagust, W., Trojanowski, J. Q., Toga, A. W., and Beckett, L., “The Alzheimer’s Disease Neuroimaging Initiative,” *Neuroimaging Clinics of North America* **15**, 869–877 (Nov. 2005).
- [24] Jagust, W. J., Bandy, D., Chen, K., Foster, N. L., Landau, S. M., Mathis, C. A., Price, J. C., Reiman, E. M., Skovronsky, D., and Koeppe, R. A., “The Alzheimer’s Disease Neuroimaging Initiative positron emission tomography core,” *Alzheimer’s & Dementia* **6**, 221–229 (May 2010).
- [25] Jagust, W. J., Landau, S. M., Koeppe, R. A., Reiman, E. M., Chen, K., Mathis, C. A., Price, J. C., Foster, N. L., and Wang, A. Y., “The Alzheimer’s Disease Neuroimaging Initiative 2 PET Core: 2015,” *Alzheimer’s & Dementia* **11**, 757–771 (July 2015).
- [26] Routier, A., Burgos, N., Díaz, M., Bacci, M., Bottani, S., El-Rifai, O., Fontanella, S., Gori, P., Guillon, J., Guyot, A., Hassanaly, R., Jacquemont, T., Lu, P., Marcoux, A., Moreau, T., Samper-González, J., Teichmann, M., Thibeau-Sutre, E., Vaillant, G., Wen, J., Wild, A., Habert, M.-O., Durrleman, S., and Colliot, O., “Clinica: An Open-Source Software Platform for Reproducible Clinical Neuroscience Studies,” *Frontiers in Neuroinformatics* **15** (Aug. 2021).
- [27] Hassanaly, R., Solal, M., Colliot, O., Burgos, N., and Disease Neuroimaging Initiative, F. T. A., “Benchmarking 3D generative autoencoders for pseudo-healthy reconstruction of brain 18F-fluorodeoxyglucose positron emission tomography,” *Journal of Medical Imaging* **12** (Oct. 2025).
- [28] Pérez-García, F., Sparks, R., and Ourselin, S., “TorchIO: A Python library for efficient loading, preprocessing, augmentation and patch-based sampling of medical images in deep learning,” *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine* **208**, 106236 (Sept. 2021).
- [29] Thibeau-Sutre, E., Díaz, M., Hassanaly, R., Routier, A., Dormont, D., Colliot, O., and Burgos, N., “ClinicaDL: An open-source deep learning software for reproducible neuroimaging processing,” *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine* **220**, 106818 (June 2022).

APPENDIX A. ADDITIONAL RESULTS: ALL EVALUATION GROUPS AND ANOMALY MAPS

A.1 Variance of models trained with different random seeds

(a) ahMSE

(b) ahSSIM

Figure 13: Reconstruction metrics per model trained with different random seed for all groups.

Figure 14: Average precision per model trained with different random seed for all groups and all anomaly maps.

A.2 Z-score to aggregate outputs from models trained with different random seeds

Figure 15: AP for all groups of all anomaly maps of models trained with random seeds 0-10 (in the x-axis, in blue) compared to $\mathbf{z}_{\text{seeds}}$ anomaly maps (in orange) built from the predictions of all models.

A.3 Normalization of anomaly maps using the healthy validation set

Figure 16: AP without (**left**) and with (**right**) healthy-control validation-based normalization for all anomaly maps.

A.4 Anomaly map design

Figure 17: Mean AP across models for each anomaly map type (without healthy-control validation-based normalization) and each evaluation group.